

Contribution of Electric Vehicles in Reduction of Greenhouse Effect with Specific Reference to Bengaluru

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Introduction

The Greenhouse effect is the process by which radiation of Earth’s atmosphere warms up the planet’s surface to the temperature what it would be. Human activities, mainly the burning of fossil fuels and deforestation have given way to greenhouse effect and global warming. The Government of India has committed to solve the greens house effect by switching to electric vehicles by 2030. The components of greenhouse gases are water vapour, carbon dioxide and methane. Electric vehicles are helpful in reducing pollution by using the renewable resources. The electric vehicles have their impact on environmental emissions and also suitable for Indian market.

Gases such as water vapour, which responds physically or chemically with other gases, namely Carbon dioxide (CO₂),Methane, Nitrous oxide, Chlorofluorocarbon (CFCs) to change in temperature in the atmosphere. As a result the Earth will become warmer and some regions on Earth may also experience warmer temperature. A stronger greenhouse effect will warm up the oceans and also melt the glaciers, increase in the sea level.

The Indian Government needs to adopt policies that increase the sale of electric vehicles, increase the percentage of renewable energy and prevent air pollution caused by the fossil fuel vehicles.

Statement of Problem

Research was scarce in the field of contribution of electric vehicles in reduction of greenhouse effect with specific reference to Bangalore covering the broad umbrella of electric vehicles in reduction of greenhouse effect from the review of literatures cited and hence it is evident no solid research has taken place in above and mentioned topic and paved the way to undertake this particular

research contribution of electric vehicles in reduction of greenhouse effect with specific reference to Bangalore.

Research Gap

From the statement of problem it is evident that there is higher scope of conducting research in the above mentioned avenue.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the ill effects of greenhouse phenomenon
2. To study how the electric vehicles are contributing towards bringing down the green house effects.
3. To suggest remedial measures for the problems coming out of the vehicles which is being run by the fossil fuels.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Charts Showing the Sales of Electrical Two Wheelers

From the above chart we can infer that the electric two wheeler industry in the country has been growing at a steady pace. EV industry of two wheeler has grown by 124 per cent upto 56,000 sales unit in FY2017-18 from 25,000 units of the previous year.

2. Chart showing the Comparison of Ather and Hero Optima Plus

From the above mentioned chart we can infer that Ather electronic two wheelers have gained more momentum in sales and is growing on a steady pace compared to Hero Optima Plus.

3. Charts Showing the Sales of Electrical Four Wheelers

From the above chart, it can be inferred that electric car sales has slumped by almost 40 per cent from 2000 units in FY2016-17 to 1200 unit in FY2017-18. However, the lack of proper infrastructure and government policies has caused a hindrance in its overall growth.

4. Chart Showing the Comparison of REVA and MAHINDRA E20

From the above chart it can be inferred that Reva has attained more sales as it was existing in the market from a very long time, though Mahindra E20 had been launched with very good additional features but people tend to buy more Reva cars than Mahindra E20 as Reva has a enormous goodwill.

5. Comparison Chart of Electronics Two Wheelers and Four Wheelers

From the above chart, unlike the EV segment in the two-wheeler market, electric cars are experiencing a dip sales due to the lack of amenities, high-battery costs and range anxiety in the country.

Findings

1. Due to the greenhouse effect the environment is affected in many ways such as increase in temperature, melting of glaciers and further increase in rise sea level and climate change.
2. As the electrical vehicles use renewable energy for functioning thus the emission by the vehicles are not hazardous.
3. Using of electrical vehicles can one of the remedial measures for reducing greenhouse effect.

Conclusion

It can be conclude that the electronic vehicles play a important role in reducing greenhouse effect.

Sugesstions

The government of India has assigned Rs 5,500 crore as part of their environmental policy, however, they are yet to offer any additional subsidy on the import of EVs into the country. The government is also yet to clarify its stand on EVs in India, with most automakers left in ambiguity towards the EV policies. This has also prevented many major automobile brands from entering the EV market in India.

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